

D1.3

Data Management Plan

31 05 2024

Mariana Malta, Tânia Moreira (INOVA+)

Document details	
Project Acronym / Name	CROPS: Curating, Replicating, Orchestrating, and Propagating Citizen Science across Europe
Project URL	http://crops-cs.eu
Project Type	Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
EU Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01
Grant Agreement No.	101131696
Project Start Date	1 January 2024
Project end date	31 December 2026
Work Package	WP1 - Coordination and management
Deliverable	D1.3 – Data Management Plan
Due date of Deliverable	31/05/2024
Actual Submission date	31/05/2024
Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable	Mariana Malta, Tânia Moreira (INOVA+)
Reviewed by	All Partners
Revision	3.0
Dissemination level	Public
Number of pages	25

Document history			
Version	Date	Comment	Modification made by
1.0	09.05.2024	First draft shared for review and comments	Mariana Malta, Tânia Moreira (INOVA+)
2.0	29.05.2024	Contributions from Partners	Giovanni Maccani (IFC) Julia Lotina (EUN) James Sprinks (EarthWatch) Arianna Liconti (OutBe) Dilek Fraisl (IIASA)
3.0	31.05.2024	Final Version	Mariana Malta, Ana Costa (INOVA+)

To cite this document:

M. Malta, T. Moreira (2024). D1.3: Data Management Plan. *Deliverable report of project Horizon Europe CROPS (Grant Agreement No. 101131696)*

Copyright

© Partners of the CROPS Consortium, 2024

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Glossary and abbreviations

DMM	Dataset Metadata Model
DMP	Data Management Plan
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ODM	Observation Data Model
PMM	Project Metadata Model
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1 Introduction.....	7
1.1 Project background.....	7
1.2 Document scope and structure	8
2 Data Summary.....	9
2.1 Data from CROPS.....	9
2.2 Data from External Sources.....	9
3 FAIR data	12
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	12
3.2 Making data accessible.....	13
3.3 Making data interoperable.....	13
3.4 Increase data re-use	13
4 Allocation of resources.....	16
4.1 Costs for making data FAIR	16
4.2 Data management responsibility	16
5 Data Security.....	17
6 Ethics	18
6.1 Sensitive Data	18
6.2 General Data Protection Regulation.....	18
6.3 Informed Consent Forms	19
6.4 Independent Ethics Advisory Board (IEAB)	20
7 Conclusion	22
Annexes	23
Annex 1: Example of Informed Consent Form for research purposes	23
Annex 2: Example of Informed Consent Form for communication and dissemination purposes.....	25

List of Tables

Table 1: Data to be generated by CROPS	10
Table 2: Key data licenses to be used by CROPS.....	14
Table 3: Access, interoperability and re-use of CROPS data	15
Table 4: Consent and Accessibility of sensitive data generated by CROPS.....	19
Table 5: Members of the Independent Ethics Advisory Board (IEAB).....	21

Executive Summary

The *Data Management Plan (DMP)* is intended to support partners in the secure and effective use and management of the data collected and generated within the CROPS project. It presents the types of research data that will be generated or collected during the project, the standards that will be used, how the research data will be preserved and what parts of the datasets will be shared for verification or reuse. CROPS will generate data from:

- Mappings
- Surveys
- Interviews (including Podcast interviews)
- Focus groups (including the Transnational Community)
- Webinars
- Workshops
- Conferences
- MOOC

The qualitative research data will not be made openly accessible as primary data but in a processed form as reports.

This DMP will be revised and updated if needed to reflect the evolving activities and needs of the project implementation, as well as to achieve a sound data management throughout.

1 Introduction

1.1 Project background

In the past decade, citizen science has become a proven and accepted methodology across a wide range of scientific disciplines, able to collect new and complementary data which both enhances and adds context to existing data collection methods. By upscaling to a transnational level, citizen science could collect, analyse, and exploit a vast amount of data across the ERA and beyond, achieving a higher impact by creating a multinational community of citizen scientists. However, many citizen science initiatives start at a small-scale, facing technical, practical, and conceptual changes when attempting to upscale to a wider level, with current EU mechanisms and other networks not providing the support, coordination or resources required to assist their effort.

CROPS aims to support the transition of citizen science from a small-scale to a Europe-wide level, moving it towards a modern, open-science approach. It will identify the most suitable citizen science initiatives for upscaling to the Europe-wide level, and in doing so it will develop protocols, resources, and examples of best practices for the upscaling of citizen science activities, helping practitioners to fully realise the potential impact of their activities towards the Horizon Europe's EU Missions. This support will be tailored to all different types of citizen science, and the different stakeholders that are involved and participation taken. CROPS will also help citizen science practitioners consider inclusivity, public trust, and societal impact, whilst being fully aware of data interoperability requirements, sustainability issues and funding approaches when upscaling their activities.

These goals will be pursued through four concurrent and interweaving activities: **(i) appraisal of existing citizen practices**, their activities and their suitability for upscaling; **(ii) creation of protocols and guidance** for the upscaling of citizen science, replicating and building on best practice that exists; **(iii) identification and guidance regarding practical considerations** such as open data sharing, sustainability, RRI and diverse funding opportunities; and **(iv) development of transnational citizen science communities**, including the establishing of societal coalitions and identification of potential citizen science champions to raise awareness of the potential of citizen science when addressing Horizon Europe EU Mission goals.

1.2 Document scope and structure

This deliverable has been developed in the context of WP1, which aims at supporting partners in the planning and implementation of the project workplan, including the production of the project's Data Management Plan (DMP).

The DMP outlined in this document details the types of data that will be generated or collected during the project, the standards to be adhered to, the methods for data preservation, and what parts of the datasets that will be available for verification or reuse.

Data for the CROPS project will be generated from:

- Mappings
- Surveys
- Interviews (including podcast interviews)
- Focus groups (including the Transnational Community)
- Webinars
- Workshops
- Conferences
- MOOC

The DMP is the result of a collaborative work of CROPS partners and serves as a support document for project partners.

This document follows the structure of "Horizon Europe - Data Management Plan Template" (version 1.1, 01 April 2022) provided by EC and available at <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents;programCode=HORIZON?programmePeriod=2021-2027&frameworkProgramme=43108390>

2 Data Summary

2.1 Data from CROPS

The CROPS project foresees several activities of data collection which is essential to achieve and ensure the quality of the project tasks and objectives. **Table 1** presents the data:

- (i) Type:** if numerical, text or other data type;
- (ii) WP:** the associated Work Package (WP) in which the activity takes place;
- (iii) Origin:** if the data will be generated (Primary data) or re-used (Secondary data)
- (iv) Storage format:** if the data will be stored in .csv, .xls, .docx, .txt, .mp3, .mp4, jpeg, or other format;
- (v) Data description and expected size:** a more detailed description of the data that will be collected and its expected size;
- (vi) Data collection purpose & to whom it be useful ('data utility'):** a description of the purpose to the data collection and to whom the data might be interesting/ benefit.

2.2 Data from External Sources

The CROPS project entails activities that will require accessing to secondary data, namely EU-wide available information on a variety of sources, including [MICS \(https://mics.tools\)](https://mics.tools). In fact, partners will review the literature (studies, white papers, consultancy reports etc.) focusing on Citizen Science initiatives linked to the five EU Missions. This collection will be essential to undertake the tasks within WPs 2, 3 and 4.

Table 1: Data to be generated by CROPS

ID	Data	Type	WP	Origin	Storage format	Data description and expected size	Data collection purpose & to whom it be useful ('data utility')
D#1	Mapping	Text, numerical	WP2 WP3 WP4	Re-used	.xls .csv .docx .pdf	<p><u>Description:</u> Review of existing processes, platforms and support regarding citizen science and its sustainability.</p> <p><u>Size:</u> Minimal. Mostly will be links and summaries of existing processes.</p>	<p><u>Purpose:</u> To understand the strengths and weaknesses of current citizen science support methodologies.</p> <p><u>Utility:</u> Syntheses of mapping activities will be shared with CS community and practitioners.</p>
D#2	Workshops	Text, audio	WP2 WP4 WP5	Generated	.xls .csv .docx .txt .mp3 .png	<p><u>Description:</u> Workshops and events involving all stakeholders of citizen science activities.</p> <p><u>Size:</u> Medium, imagery and audio along with syntheses of outcomes.</p>	<p><u>Purpose:</u> To better understand the concerns and views of stakeholders regarding the sustainability of citizen science and its upscaling.</p> <p><u>Utility:</u> To involve all stakeholders in CROPS solutions and outputs.</p>
D#3	Surveys	Text, numerical	WP3 WP4 WP6	Generated	.xls .docx .txt	<p><u>Description:</u> #1 Surveys (online) to widen the involvement of stakeholders and increase accessibility. #2 Pre-course surveys (online) to collect participants' personal data and post-course surveys to gather feedback on the MOOC experience and suggestions. All data will remain anonymous. An identification code will be assigned to facilitate comparison between responses in the pre- and post-surveys.</p> <p><u>Size:</u> Minimal. Text and scores from survey responses.</p>	<p><u>Purpose:</u> #1 To better understand the concerns and views of stakeholders regarding the sustainability of citizen science and its upscaling. #2 Gather participants' feedback on the MOOC, as well as generic data on their background.</p> <p><u>Utility:</u> #1 To involve all stakeholders in CROPS solutions and outputs. #2 Data will be useful for EUN and project partners in all WPs.</p>
D#4	Interviews	Text, audio	WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5	Generated	.mp3 .docx .txt	<p><u>Description:</u> investigate and explore pathways for upscaling.</p> <p><u>Size:</u> Medium, imagery and audio along with syntheses of outcomes.</p>	<p><u>Purpose:</u> understand upscaling processes and inhibitors and generate best practices.</p> <p><u>Utility:</u> All partners and all WPs in CROPS.</p>

D#5	Photos and/or video collection	Text, image, audio	WP6	Generated	.png .mp4	<p><u>Description:</u> photos, videos, and multimedia material to be collected for dissemination purposes to show-cast the value of citizen science</p> <p><u>Size:</u> to be determined</p>	<p><u>Purpose:</u> to be shared on our social media channels, conferences and in dissemination-related spheres.</p> <p><u>Utility:</u> share the actions, deliverables, and milestones of CROPS, disseminate the value, importance and ways of upscaling citizen science.</p>
D#6	Learning Scenarios	Text, image	WP6	Generated and re-used	.docx .pdf	<p><u>Description:</u> EUN together with teachers will be developing Learning Scenarios on citizen science. Some Learning Scenarios will also be collected and further curated as part of the STEM Discovery Campaign 2025.</p> <p><u>Size:</u> To be determined.</p>	<p><u>Purpose:</u> Offering teachers ideas and examples on how to integrate citizen science into their lessons.</p> <p><u>Utility:</u> Learning Scenarios are primarily addressed to teachers.</p>
D#7	MOOC	Text, image, audio	WP6	Generated and re-used	.png .mp4 .docx .pdf	<p><u>Description:</u> A MOOC on citizen science will be developed, tailored primarily for educators. The course will leverage existing educational resources, guidelines, reports, and audiovisual materials to shape its content. Additionally, new materials will be curated and produced.</p> <p><u>Size:</u> To be determined.</p>	<p><u>Purpose:</u> Development of a MOOC on citizen science.</p> <p><u>Utility:</u> Support educators and other relevant stakeholders in learning about citizen science and incorporate it into their teaching practices.</p>
D#8	Citizen Science Champions Podcast	Audio, images, text	WP5	Generated and re-used	.mp3 .png .docx	<p><u>Description:</u> Audio files from interviews of citizen science champions will be shared as a podcast on Spotify, alongside their profile pictures and text to advertise the champion on our website and episode description.</p> <p><u>Size:</u> max 40 minutes audio files, 20 pictures and minimal text</p>	<p><u>Purpose:</u> Share the stories behind champions of citizen science.</p> <p><u>Utility:</u> Elevate public understanding and support of citizen science, inspire citizens to take actions, share success stories for citizen science managers and policymakers.</p>

3 FAIR data

Following the guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon Europe, the next subsections present the main considerations of CROPS partners to ensure proper sharing and management of the data collected and generated during the project.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data and project results will be disseminated to relevant communities through publications and open access data repositories.

An important aspect in making data findable is the adoption of a suitable naming convention for project data. In this sense:

Datasets generated during the project will use a name convention as follows:

CROPS_WPxx_Txx_DDMMYYYY_.doc, i.e. acronym of the project + WP generating the dataset + Task generating the dataset + data of creation with format DDMMYYYY + dataset format.

As for project reports/deliverables, name segments should be as follows:

CROPS_D1.1_31012024_V01.doc – meaning that the report consists of Version 1 of the Deliverable D1.1 produced on 31 January 2024.

The CROPS metadata will be deposited under a Creative Common License (CC BY-NC-ND 4.0, CC BY-SA 4.0 DEED) and at least the following information will be provided:

- Datasets (description, author(s), publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable);
- Horizon Europe funding;
- Grant project name, acronym, and number;
- Licensing terms;
- Persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

3.2 Making data accessible

CROPS will offer open access to data generated and outputs, as well as to relevant publications and reports produced throughout the project lifetime.

By default, results generated by users and partners will be open under a Creative Commons license (CC BY-NC-ND 4.0, CC BY-SA 4.0 DEED).

The CROPS website and associated resources will be designed to include language and accessibility support.

Furthermore, relevant datasets will be stored in [CROPS website](#), [ZENODO](#) - the open access repository of Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) – and [EU-Citizen.Science](#) – the EU platform focuses on citizen science projects. Datasets might also be shared through the repositories reviewed as part of D4.1: Open data repositories analysis report (M18), if deemed appropriate.

3.3 Making data interoperable

The data and outputs produced and/or used in the project should be interoperable allowing data exchange between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc.

Descriptions and cataloguing of associated citizen science activities will be carried out following the [PPSR-Core](#) standards, that include: (i) Project Metadata Model (PMM), (ii) Dataset Metadata Model (DMM); and (iii) Observation Data Model (ODM). In this context, Citizen Science Association' [PPSR-Core](#) and the [EC COST Action](#) (some consortium partners are members of both) on data standardisation and interoperability will serve as a baseline for good data practice.

3.4 Increase data re-use

The data collected and the outputs generated will be made available for re-use.

To maximize data and outputs re-use a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes will be employed, in accordance with the [PPSR-Core](#) nomenclature.

Data will be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible when no limitations are identified by the key stakeholders. The following licenses will be mainly used:

Table 2: Key data licenses to be used by CROPS

The user is free to	Under the following terms
<p>CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International. [URL]</p>	<p>Attribution - You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.</p> <p>Non-commercial - You may not use the material for commercial purposes.</p> <p>No Derivatives - If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you may not distribute the modified material.</p> <p>No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.</p>
<p>CC BY-SA 4.0 DEED Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International. [URL]</p>	<p>Share - copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format for any purpose, even commercially.</p> <p>Adapt - remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.</p> <p>Attribution - You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.</p> <p>ShareAlike - If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.</p>

Table 3 provides details for each type of data generated by the project concerning its accessibility, interoperability, and re-use.

Table 3: Access, interoperability, and re-use of CROPS data

ID	Data	Access	Interoperability	Re-use
D#1	Mapping	Mapping syntheses and outputs will be accessible through project website and repositories	All outputs will be in common formats, following any existing protocols of the resources mapped.	Will follow licences of resources mapped
D#2	Workshops	Workshop findings and outputs will be aggregated, anonymised, and shared on project website, repositories, and through deliverables and publications	All outputs will be in common formats, with metadata schemes where appropriate.	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0
D#3	Surveys	Survey findings and outputs will be aggregated, anonymised, and shared on project website, repositories, and through deliverables and publications	All outputs will be in common formats, with metadata schemes where appropriate.	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0
D#4	Interviews	Conclusions gathered in reports to be accessible in project website, social media and other platforms. Generated data accessible by contacting main authors. Data must be shared after anonymised process.	Interoperability ensured by commonly known research language.	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0
D#5	Photos and/or video collection	Accessible in project website, social media and other platforms.	Not allowed. The data is not suitable for interoperability.	
D#6	Learning Scenarios	Accessible in the project website and Scientix Resource Repository. Some Learning Scenarios might also be accessible in the MOOC platform at European Schoolnet Academy.	All outputs will be in common formats, with metadata schemes where appropriate.	CC BY-SA 4.0 DEED
D#7	MOOC	Registration for the MOOC is free. After the course is completed, it will remain available for self-paced learning on the European Schoolnet Academy platform for five years.	All outputs will be in common formats, with metadata schemes where appropriate.	CC BY-SA 4.0 DEED
D#8	Citizen Science Champions Podcast	The podcast episodes will remain freely available on Spotify until further notice, while the online profiles will remain on CROPS website until the end of the project.	All outputs will be in common formats, with metadata schemes where appropriate.	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0
D#9	Stakeholders contacts lists	Non-public. The lists gather sensitive data (e.g. names, contacts). It will remain private and for CROPS partners use only.	Not allowed. The lists will not be made publicly available.	

4 Allocation of resources

4.1 Costs for making data FAIR

For all foreseen measures, already existing platforms and infrastructure are used and there is no extra budget foreseen in the Grant Agreement for making data FAIR, as no additional costs will arise from making data FAIR.

4.2 Data management responsibility

In accordance with the [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/679](#), each consortium partner will act as Data Controller and will be responsible for managing and controlling the data they collect and for ensuring that the DMP is carried out. INOVA+, as the project coordinator, will also serve as the Data Controller for the project management coordination.

During the project' implementation, data management responsibilities will be distributed among the partners according to their specific roles and tasks. However, primary oversight will be provided by the project coordinator (as Data Controller), in collaboration with the work package leaders. The latter are responsible for ensuring the effective implementation of data management procedures within their respective WPs.

Internal and confidential information, personal data, and sensitive data such as financial information will be treated confidentially. Compliance with relevant data protection legislation, including the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), will be maintained. All personal data will be anonymised as appropriate and/or pseudonymised before it is published externally, except for the videos with citizen science experts or Learning Scenarios that will include their names and necessary information.

INOVA+, as the project coordinator, will ensure the long-term curation and preservation of the data beyond the project period, for a minimum of five years.

5 Data Security

To ensure secure storage and handling of CROPS' data, the following procedures shall be followed by members of the CROPS consortium:

- Store data in at least two separate locations.
- Storage of proof of consent (i.e. copies and/or originals of signed consent forms) separately from the collected data.
- Implementing appropriate access limitations on the folders shared on collaborative platforms (i.e. SharePoint)
- Perform regular and appropriate backups.
- Encrypt data when necessary.
- Label files in a systematically structured way to ensure the coherence of the final dataset (as described in 2.1).
- Limit the use of USB flash drives.

Data is to be stored in the project **SharePoint on Microsoft Teams** which is password-protected and only accessible by partners. Internal datasets will be regularly backed up for future retrieval to support re-use or verification.

Public deliverables will include thorough descriptions of information and data. They will be systematically archived on the project website ([CROPS Deliverables](#)), as well as on [ZENODO](#), EU-Citizen.Science and on the EU's Community Research and Development Information Service ([CORDIS](#)). The podcast interviews will be archived on [Spotify](#).

The project's commitment to Open Access and the use of repositories aims to facilitate the unrestricted availability of research data and publications.

Data stored on SharePoint will be kept for 5 years after the end of the project and made available for third parties upon request. Data archived in other platforms will be available according to the repository access 'rules.

6 Ethics

CROPS and all those involved from beneficiary and partner organisations will conduct research and **commit to abide strictly to the following principles:**

- Respect human dignity and integrity.
- Ensure honesty and transparency towards participants and notably getting free and informed consent.
- Protect vulnerable persons.
- Ensure privacy and confidentiality.
- Share the benefits with disadvantaged populations.
- Follow the highest standards of research integrity (i.e. avoiding any kind of fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, unjustified double funding, or other type of research misconduct) as defined in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

6.1 Sensitive Data

At the heart of CROPS is the experience of stakeholders, and other interested parties and actors, in citizen science activities. As such the project will process data of **human participants**, particularly through the collection of data during evaluation and co-creation activities (e.g.: workshops, interviews, and surveys), as part of a user-centred design process.

The CROPS project team is particularly aware of the sensitivity of collected data, most importantly participant demographic and contact details. Ethics considerations will be addressed consistently across all Work Packages.

CROPS consortium partners have extensive experience with this type of work and the needed methodology as well as ethics approval requirements and processes, including informed consent, treatment of personal data, safeguarding personal interests, anonymisation, and publication of results in compliant ways were properly assured.

6.2 General Data Protection Regulation

CROPS will comply with the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon Europe regulations that apply the EU GDPR ([2016/679](#)), and in accordance with the international and EU Directives/Regulations, as well as respective national iterative.

To the extent possible, all data will be anonymised as appropriate or pseudonymised when stored or shared, and the consortium will follow strict ethical reviews when designing the methods for data collection and analysis. All personal data will be handled in line with the GDPR (EU) 2016/679 as well as with the national privacy laws and regulations by which the consortium partners are bound.

6.3 Informed Consent Forms

All participants attending face-to-face or online CROPS activities (for research or other purposes, such as communication and dissemination) will receive Participant Information Sheets and will be asked to provide clear acceptance (either orally or written authorisations) of CROPS Consent Forms before participation (see **Annex 1 and 2**, which include examples of Informed Consent Forms).

Participants will be given information about how their data will be collected, protected during the project and either destroyed or re-used at the end of the project. In the latter case, they will be reminded that they may withhold such data; and that any such additional activities will remain strictly within the bounds covered by their informed consent form.

Non-professional personal data, if collected, will be stored securely on a password-protected computer, only used for the purpose for which it was collected. If a plan to re-use data is considered, participants will be given information about this as soon as it becomes available and be given the opportunity to consent or withdraw their data.

Table 4: Consent and Accessibility of Sensitive Data Generated by CROPS

Data	Consent	Accessibility of sensitive data
Mapping	Not required. All data and resources mapped will already be openly available and have gone through an original consent process where required.	No sensitive data is shared. All data and resources mapped are already openly available.
Workshops	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agree with the consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Data is shared after the anonymization process.
Surveys	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agreed with the consent form. The materials are	No sensitive data is shared. Data is shared after the anonymization process.

	used for the agreed options.	
Interviews	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agree with the consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Data is shared after the anonymization process.
Stakeholders contacts lists	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agree with the consent form. Their contacts are used for the agreed options.	Only accessible by CROPS partners.
Photos and/ or video collection	Yes. Stakeholders are requested to read and agree with the consent form. The materials are used for the agreed options.	No sensitive data is shared. Materials are publicly available under restricted license.
Teacher contracts	Yes.	Financial data will be collected. EUN has put in place appropriate technical and security measures to protect the premises, systems, applications, and databases where sensitive data is stored against accidental loss, alteration, disclosure or use or access in an unauthorised way. EUN processes only the personal data required for achieving the purposes communicated to the data subjects and restricts access to personal data collected as part of this task to EUN staff working on the project.
Citizen Science Champions Podcast	Yes, all interviewed have agreed to the recording and sharing of the interviews in the recording and via email.	No sensitive data is shared. Materials produced with consent are publicly available.

6.4 Ethics Advisory Board (EAB)

To augment the consortium's internal expertise on ethics and ensure the highest standards are maintained throughout the entire project lifetime, an independent ethics advisor was appointed and will be a key part of the advisory board.

The EAB will be asked to:

- **Ethical review:** Conducting ethical reviews of methodological procedures to ensure that they comply with relevant ethical standards, legal regulations, and data protection laws.
- **Informed consent:** Ensuring that informed consent processes are appropriately designed and implemented, particularly concerning the collection, storage, and use of sensitive or personal data.

- **Data Protection:** Overseeing privacy measures to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of participant data throughout its lifecycle.
- **Risk Assessment:** Conduct risk assessments to identify potential ethical issues or risks associated with data management practices and proposing mitigation strategies where necessary.
- **Participant protection:** Ensuring the protection of participants' rights, including the right to privacy, dignity, and confidentiality, throughout the data management process.
- **Data access and sharing:** Reviewing protocols for data access and sharing to ensure responsible and ethical practices, balancing openness with the protection of participants' rights.

Table 5: Members of the Ethics Advisory Board (EAB)

Name	Gender	Country	Partner Organization
Liz Dowthwaite	Female	UK	EarthWatch
James Sprinks	Male	UK	EarthWatch
Giovanni Maccani	Male	Spain	IFC
Julia Lotina	Female	Belgium	EUN
Arianna Liconti	Female	Italy	OutBe
Dilek Fraisl	Female	Austria	IIASA
Mariana Malta	Female	Portugal	INOVA+

7 Conclusion

D1.3 Data Management Plan serves as a comprehensive guide for partners, detailing the types of data generated, accessibility, licensing, reuse, resource allocation, security measures and ethical considerations. The project partners are fully committed to fulfilling their respective responsibilities as mentioned throughout the document. However, they also acknowledge that as the project progresses, new guidelines and practices may need to be established to address evolving needs or challenges. In such cases, the Data Management Plan will be updated accordingly. Any updates or changes made to the document will be communicated to all partners and duly reported in the prefinancing and/or periodic report.

Annexes

Annex 1: Example of Informed Consent Form for research purposes

CONSENT FORM

Date: [Insert date]

Project: CROPS

Ethics Reference: CR001

Funded by: This project funded by the European Union (GA 101131696)

Please tick the appropriate boxes

Yes No

1. Taking part in the study

- a) I have read and understood the project information sheet dated [DD/MM/YYYY], or it has been read to me. I have been able to ask questions about the study and my questions have been answered satisfactorily. Yes No
- b) I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study and understand that I can refuse to answer questions and I can withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason. Yes No
- d) I understand that taking part in the study requires me to provide data and that this will involve filling out questionnaires and surveys, taking part in discussions on environmental impact, and creating new ideas and designs for communicating CROPS products. Yes No

2. Use of my data in the study

- a) I understand that data which can identify me will not be shared beyond the project team. Yes No
- b) I agree that the data provided by me may be used for the following purposes:
- Presentation and discussion of the project and its results in research activities (e.g., in supervision sessions, project meetings, conferences). Yes No
 - Publications and reports describing the project and its results. Yes No
 - Dissemination of the project and its results, including publication of data on web pages and databases. Yes No
- c) I give permission for my words to be quoted for the purposes described above. Yes No
- d) I give permission for my visual image contained in photos or video gathered during the research to be used for the purposes described above. Yes No

Please tick the appropriate boxes

Yes No

3. Reuse of my data

- a) I give permission for the data that I provide to be reused for the sole purposes of future research and learning. Yes No
- b) I understand and agree that this may involve depositing my data in a data repository, which may be accessed by other researchers Yes No

4. Security of my data

- a) I understand that safeguards will be put in place to protect my identity and my data during the research, and if my data is kept for future use. Yes No
- b) I confirm that a written copy of these safeguards has been given to me in the Earthwatch privacy notice, and that they have been described to me and are acceptable to me. Yes No
- c) I understand that no computer system is completely secure and that there is a risk that a third party could obtain a copy of my data. Yes No

5. Copyright

- a) I give permission for data gathered during this project to be used, copied, excerpted, annotated, displayed and distributed for the purposes to which I have consented. Yes No
- b) I wish to be publicly identified as the creator of the following works: designs to promote CROPS products and methods. Yes No

6. Signatures (sign as appropriate)

Name of participant (IN CAPITALS)	Signature	Date
-----------------------------------	-----------	------

If applicable:
 For participants unable to sign their name, mark the box instead of signing

I have witnessed the accurate reading of the consent form with the participant and the individual has had the opportunity to ask questions. I confirm that the individual has given consent freely.

Name of witness (IN CAPITALS)	Signature	Date
-------------------------------	-----------	------

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant and, to the best of my ability, ensured that the participant understands to what they are freely consenting.

--	--	--

Annex 2: Example of Informed Consent Form for communication and dissemination purposes

Photography/filming consent form

Name of CROPS researcher: *To be completed by CROPS staff*

Name of photographer/filmmaker: *To be completed by CROPS staff*

Name of adult / parent / guardian	
Location of Photography (or school if applicable)	<i>To be completed by CROPS staff</i>
Date of photography/filming	<i>To be completed by CROPS staff</i>
<p>By completing this form you are consenting to the CROPS consortium taking photos and/or video footage of you and/or your child.</p> <p>We may use these images and videos to illustrate the work of CROPS on our websites, email newsletters and social media channels; in our printed materials including leaflets, posters, and adverts; in materials sent out to the media; or in reports and presentations.</p> <p>Please note that some channels, particularly online, can be seen throughout the world, and not just in the EU, where EU law applies.</p> <p>© Copyright of the photographs and video footage taken for CROPS will remain with the CROPS consortium. We will not publish the full names of children in relation to an image.</p> <p>CROPS is funded by the European Union (GA 101131696). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. To find out how we use your data and how long we keep it for please see our full privacy policy https://www.crops-cs.eu/privacy.</p>	

Your signature:	
Date:	